

EXPLOITING DOMAIN KNOWLEDGE IN MUSIC INFORMATION RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

Music Information Research (MIR) is a discipline that aims to understand and model music from an information processing perspective, but the successful approaches used in MIR are going beyond the traditional data processing methodologies. Most of the great advancements have been the result of combining engineering disciplines such as audio signal processing and machine learning with non-engineering disciplines such as music perception and music theory. One of the challenges in MIR is to automatically describe music audio signals, thus to develop methodologies to extract musically useful information from audio recordings. In this paper we claim that if we want to advance in this direction we should maximize the use of musical knowledge in all the steps of our research tasks. To support this claim we overview some of the work being carried out in CompMusic, a project that aims to analyze and automatically describe the music of several non-western music traditions.

1. INTRODUCTION

The field of MIR has greatly grown in the past two decades and the number of disciplines involved has expanded. The MIR research community is evolving and changing accordingly, specially due to the incorporation of researchers coming from fields such as Speech Processing, Text Retrieval or Computer Vision. These changes might have been influential in the fact that most of the current research is centered in data processing methodologies, thus with a bottom-up perspective. Most of the approaches used are not specific to musical problems and there is a recent agreement in the community on the need to explore new methodological approaches that can complement the currently used data processing ones.

The recently published MIR roadmap [1] identifies current research challenges while reviewing the relevant state of the art. It lists challenges related to the gathering and organization of machine-readable musical data, to the development of data representations, and to the methodologies for processing and understanding that data, taking into

account domain knowledge and bringing expertise from relevant scientific and engineering disciplines. The Roadmap also looks into a user perspective, thus promoting the need to understand the user roles within the music communication chain and to develop technologies for the interaction of these users with music data. Finally, the roadmap emphasizes the fact that music is a communication phenomenon that involves people and communities immersed in specific social and cultural contexts, thus it claims that MIR should aim at developing methodologies for processing musical data that capture these contexts.

There is a widespread consensus in the MIR community on the need to emphasize knowledge-driven methodologies. Collaboration should be promoted with disciplines such as Musicology, Psychology, and Sociology. But the key question is: how can we use the knowledge generated from these disciplines as part of the methodologies being used in MIR?

Most MIR projects are carried out following a common set of steps. After defining the problem, the data to be analyzed is gathered, a methodology is developed to process the data, experiments are run in which the methods are applied to the data, and finally the results are evaluated. The main point that we want to emphasize in this paper is the need to use musical knowledge, domain knowledge, in every one of these steps. The problem, the data, the method and the evaluation steps, all have to be musically meaningful and musically relevant. Many published articles have not given enough consideration to the musical issues and as a result the obtained results lack the impact intended by the authors.

The most direct way of adding domain knowledge in a research project is by incorporating domain experts in the research team. This is fundamental. But even then, how can we represent and express specific musical concepts in the data and methodologies used in an MIR project? Given that many music traditions have developed and use formalizations/representations in the education and transmission of their music, a good starting point are the formalisms developed by the music scholars of those traditions. These formalisms can then be incorporated into the MIR-specific computational methodologies.

Next we present some issues related to musical knowledge representation and then we go over how we address these issues in the CompMusic project.

2. MUSICAL KNOWLEDGE REPRESENTATION

Knowledge engineering is a discipline that involves integrating knowledge into computer systems in order to solve complex problems normally requiring a high level of human expertise. In the currently favored modeling view of the field, the knowledge engineer attempts to model the knowledge and problem solving techniques of the domain expert.¹ A major concern in knowledge engineering is the construction of domain specific ontologies, which are structural frameworks for organizing information and that are used as a form of knowledge representations [2].

Music is a complex phenomenon that can be approached and studied from a multitude of perspectives. Even the definition of music vary according to culture and social context.² From a knowledge engineering perspective the only way to agree on a set of musical formalisms and concepts is to narrow down the domain to a level in which we can find a sufficient scholarly consensus, without reaching a domain size so small that is of no use. A practical approximation is to constrain the domain to a particular music culture and to a particular application. For example, the Music Ontology project³ is developing and maintaining several ontologies of music production concepts and it is basically centered on western commercial music. In the CompMusic project we have decided to focus on five music cultures and we are working towards the particular application of music discovery of audio content.

An ontology specifies concepts, attributes, relations, constraints, and instances in a domain. For creating music ontologies the most useful types of information sources are the encyclopaedias and dictionaries, ideally written by music scholars specialists on the chosen domain. From these sources we can gather all the relevant concepts used in a specific domain area, but it is not easy to gather the relations between concepts. Musicological books and articles are very useful but they are often not precise enough for extracting clearly formalized concepts and relationships. At the same time it is not easy to find clear agreement between different information sources, thus there is always the need to involve domain experts and to account for the fact that there are no single and long-lived formalizations. No matter what information source we start from, even written by the most academically reputed scholar, it will be impossible to come up with complete and persistent ontologies. Thus, we should develop systems that can handle multiple versions of an ontology and that can support dynamic ontologies.

There has been little work in the development of domain specific ontologies for music and efforts are needed to create them. The existing and most related initiatives are the repositories of structured information that are being created as collaborative on-line projects. Two of the larger and most important projects of relevance to music are Musicbrainz⁴ and DBpedia.⁵

MusicBrainz is an open music encyclopedia that collects music metadata and makes it available to the public. It aims to form a trusty central database to identify music CDs. In MusicBrainz anyone can add the metadata of CDs such as the names of tracks, the label of the release and the artists featured in the album. Yet, MusicBrainz is more ambitious than just being a database of metadata of CDs, it also allows to add detailed information about the music, such as personal details of artists, composer/lyricist information, or the specific date of a performance. Even more, the MusicBrainz database can maintain relationships between the data entities.

The DBpedia project is a community effort to extract structured information from Wikipedia and to make this information available on the Web. Through DBpedia we can ask sophisticated queries against Wikipedia, and we can link different data sets on the Web to Wikipedia data. DBpedia is at the core of the W3C Linking Opendata community effort⁶ and MusicBrainz is the main music project within that community. All the information generated by these projects is available as open data sets using the RDF specification. These RDF links enable to navigate between data items in various data sources using a search language like SPARQL.⁷

In the context of MIR we are interested in describing and organizing the musical concepts and entities observed in audio recordings, scores, and writings on music. We generally get data/information both from existing data repositories and from the processing of the data. The automatic, or semiautomatic, structuring and integration of all this information is one of the main research efforts in MIR.

3. THE CASE OF COMPMUSIC

In the CompMusic project we work on the automatic description of music by emphasizing the use of domain knowledge of particular music traditions. We are focusing on five music cultures: Turkish-makam (Turkey), Arab-Andalusian (Maghreb), Beijing Opera (China), Carnatic (South-India) and Hindustani (North-India). There are many great traditions that we could have also chosen, but we had to limit ourselves and we were looking for traditions that: (1) had musical personalities contrasting with the popular western music of the last few decades, (2) had alive performance practices and strong social and cultural relevance, (3) had musicological and cultural studies available about them, and (4) it was feasible to collect sufficient and coherent machine-readable music data. At the same time we wanted to have a diverse set of music repertoires to study a variety of new and diverse MIR problems. The target application of CompMusic is to develop a system to browse through audio music collections of the chosen cultures, a system with which to discover characteristics of the music and relationships between different musical concepts. For a list of articles resulting from this research we refer to the project's website.⁸

¹ http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Knowledge_engineering

² <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Music>

³ <http://musicontology.com/>

⁴ <http://musicbrainz.org>

⁵ <http://dbpedia.org>

⁶ <http://www.w3.org/wiki/SweoIG/TaskForces/CommunityProjects/LinkingOpenData>

⁷ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SPARQL>

⁸ <http://compmusic.upf.edu>

Figure 1. Diagram of the tasks being carried out in CompMusic for every musical culture.

Figure 1 shows a diagram of the specific research tasks that are being carried out for all the music traditions. However, in order to emphasize our point, here we overview CompMusic by going through the basic and most common tasks in MIR projects.

3.1 Problem definition

Defining relevant problems is the single most important step in any research project. For the case of CompMusic we wanted to work on problems that could take advantage of the musical specificities of each tradition and that could result in technologies for musically meaningful explorations of audio music collections. This is a large project and thus we were able to be ambitious in the problem formulations.

In the five music traditions chosen, melody and rhythm are, arguably, the two most important musical facets. At the same time each tradition has a different way to understand both melody and rhythm. These complementary facts offer the possibility to focus on just these two musical facets while being able to explore a large variety of problems and methodologies.

In the project we have involved music experts and researchers coming from all the cultures we are studying. With their input we have defined specific problems to work on. Impossible to detail here all the identified issues; so let's just mention the basic concepts that are framing most of our automatic music description tasks. In the Indian traditions *rāga* and *tāla* are the driving melodic and rhythmic concepts and in Turkish-makam music the corresponding melodic and rhythmic frameworks are the *makam* and *usul*. In Arab-Andalusian music the *nawba* is a fundamental structuring concept that defines the melodic and rhythmic characteristics and in Beijing Opera the *shengqiang* and the *banshi* are the basic concepts underlying melody and meter. We could go very deep into each of these concepts but for the purpose of MIR, given that we are just starting in this direction, basic musicological studies have been sufficient for defining the musical issues of relevance for our project, at least for now.

3.2 Data collections

Properly collecting and organizing the data is a crucial and demanding task. The basic types of machine readable data used in CompMusic are: audio recordings, editorial metadata, scores, and social data. In the research done so far we have focused on the audio recordings and the accompanying metadata.

Experts advised us in the selection of the CDs for each repertoire, with the goal to gather in the course of the project at least 500 hours of curated audio per collection. For the selection of the CDs it was important to choose recordings by recognized and representative artists, with reliable editorial information. As a result of musical and research considerations each collection has special characteristics. For example the Carnatic collection is basically composed of live recordings of concerts and the Beijing Opera collection is composed of CDs in which a single artist sings a compilation of arias.

To store the editorial metadata of the CDs we use MusicBrainz. However MusicBrainz was designed to support western popular music and it lacks the support for some of our culture specific concepts. Given the community-based development of MusicBrainz, we are involved in the addition of the culture specific concepts that we need and in contributing to make sure that it can properly support our music repertoires. For example, MusicBrainz now supports most of the instruments used in our music traditions and we are in the way to add support for concepts such as *rāga* and *tāla*.

The musical cultures studied have developed as oral traditions but they also use music notations, scores, and these are useful to study and describe some musical characteristics. However few scores are available in machine readable form and so far we have been able to gather a well curated collection of scores for Turkish-makam music.⁹ It has been easier to obtain the lyrics, also very relevant, of the vocal pieces that we are gathering, which represent a large percentage of all our music.

Social data is a valuable source of information to work on issues like community profiling. The challenge is to identify on-line communities with discussion forums dedicated to particular music traditions and available to be crawled and studied computationally. So far we have identified and studied an on-line community for Carnatic music.¹⁰

3.3 Data processing

The most common data processing methodologies used in MIR come from the fields of signal processing and machine learning; being both extensively used in CompMusic.

With signal processing methods we extract features from audio recordings, in our case features that describe melodic and rhythmic characteristics of the music. We focus on audio features that are perceptually relevant and on top of which we can apply music considerations. Features that we extract include: prominent pitch, intonation profiles [3],

⁹ SymbTr (<http://compmusic.upf.edu/node/140>)

¹⁰ <http://www.rasikas.org/forum/index.php>

loudness, note onset location, and brightness. These are meaningful features that can be used to study and to describe musical concepts and at the same time they are basic features from which to extract higher level descriptors. To compute these features we use Essentia,¹¹ an audio analysis library developed by our research group.

With machine learning methods we obtain higher level descriptors and identify musically meaningful categories. For example we have computed the tonic pitch for the case of indian music [4] and performed structural segmentations of many pieces. A fundamental problem of the machine learning methods is that they behave like black boxes, solving a given task without helping much in the understanding of the solution. For our purposes we try to minimize this problem by using well selected and musically meaningful features as input and by emphasizing supervised approaches in which the training set has been labelled by music experts. Also we choose machine learning methods, like decision trees, that generate explicit rules that might be easier to understand, specially if the number of input features is small.

One of the key research problems in CompMusic is the identification and characterization of melodic and rhythmic patterns. For this task we need to develop meaningful similarity measures so we can compare patterns from the extracted audio features and organize them into categories. Important here is to use melody and rhythm representations that make sense for the given culture and that can be invariant to non-relevant music transformations, such as transposition and tempo change. So far we have applied some supervised approaches using dynamic time warping methods [5].

The most common bottleneck in statistical and machine learning methods are the training sets. In CompMusic we have put a lot of effort in having data collections for training that are carefully labelled by experts. We are working towards having complete ontologies that can capture all the relevant attributes and relationships of the data and metadata of each collection, thus resulting in well structured training sets that can be used in a variety of problems.

3.4 Evaluation

The evaluation has become a fundamental part of any MIR project and there is much concern on developing proper evaluations at the system level [6]. To evaluate an MIR system we have to characterize the usage experience of the users who will employ it, thus we need to have a system with a clear application and identified target users.

For the case of CompMusic we are developing technologies with which to discover musically relevant relationships within specific audio music collections and our target users are the music lovers of the particular music tradition that the collection belongs to. To carry proper evaluations we are developing a web-based software application, Dunya,¹² that lets users interact with an audio music collection using the technologies developed in the project.

The application displays the content of various culture specific entities and their relationships. Users can listen to the recordings and navigate through the collection by exploring information that is related to the currently viewed entity, either through links that reflect ontological relationships or by using culturally relevant similarity measures.

We are evaluating specific technologies using ground truth data and we will evaluate the overall Dunya system with user tests. Not many evaluations have yet been done but we will make sure that the user evaluation results are used for improving the technologies being developed.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Music Information Research is a field very much tied to the domain that it studies, Music. Any music information processing task reaches a glass ceiling quite early on unless domain knowledge is added into the research methodology. In this article we have argued in favour of this point by using as example the problem of automatically describing audio recording of specific music cultures for the purpose of discovering relationship between the entities that can be identified in them. The project CompMusic started two years ago and has three more years to go, but with the obtained results we have already shown the usefulness of exploiting domain knowledge.

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